

A KINETIC AND MICROSTRUCTURAL STUDY OF OXIDE, CARBIDE,
AND NITRIDE DIFFUSION BARRIERS IN HSTW (TUNGSTEN)
REINFORCED MAR-M-200 COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A kinetic study of diffusion barriers between the tungsten wire reinforcement and superalloy matrix for HSTW/Mar-M-200 composites was conducted over the temperature range 1066° to 1177°C (1950 to 2150°F). R.f. sputter deposited coatings of Al₂O₃, Y₂O₃, HfO₂, TiC and HfC were applied to 0.051 cm (0.02 in.) dia. HSTW (tungsten 2% ThO₂) wire to a depth of 4 to 12 μ m. In addition, chemically vapor deposited TiN was applied to 0.038 cm (0.015 in.) dia. W-1 ThO₂ wire. The coated wires were HIP consolidated in argon atomized Mar-M-200 powder for 2 hrs. at 1120°C (2050°F) at a pressure of 69 MPa (10 ksi) to form the diffusion couples.

The couples were heated for as long as 2000 hrs. at 1177°C and evaluated for Ni penetration into the tungsten wire by observing the depth of the Ni-enhanced recrystallization zone. Of all the coating candidates, only HfC proved to be an effective barrier at 1177°C (2150°F) with only 16 μ m of total Ni penetration into the HSTW (tungsten) wire. HfC was also the only acceptable barrier candidate at 1121°C with no detectable recrystallization of the HSTW tungsten wire after a 1000 hr. exposure. However, HfO₂, Y₂O₃, Al₂O₃ and HfC appeared to be effective barriers at 1066°C (1950°F) with TiN also being acceptable.

Chemical analysis of the barriers utilizing EDX, EMA, XRD and scanning Auger spectroscopy revealed a gross change in composition of even the successful HfC coating. HfC was found to suffer from carbon partitioning with matrix constituents and in-situ formation of HfO₂, HfSiO₄ and Al₂O₃ rich mixed oxide formation at the coating-matrix interface.

Introduction

The strength of tungsten wire at intermediate temperatures (to 1200°C) is derived from the stable fine fibrous substructure produced during wire drawing. The substructure is stabilized by potassium bubbles⁽¹⁾ or by finely dispersed ThO₂ particles in case of HSTW wire. These structures are extremely stable and contrary to most materials⁽²⁾ the recrystallization temperature of potassium or ThO₂ doped tungsten increases with increasing amounts of cold work to a saturation level at some value above 2000°C depending upon the in-process annealing history as shown in Figure 1.⁽³⁾

Fig. 1 -- Variation of tensile strength and corresponding variation of recrystallization temperature of HR tungsten with cold work of wire drawing.

The attractive tensile and creep properties of unrecrystallized tungsten wire at temperatures as high as 1200°C (4) have resulted in the consideration of HSTW (high strength thoriated tungsten), W-Hf-C and W-Re-Hf-C as reinforcement candidates for high temperature superalloy/refractory metal wire composite turbine blades. (4-7)

Previous investigators (8-13) have shown that certain matrix elements, i.e., Ni, Al, Cr, Co, interdiffuse into tungsten wires and cause recrystallization of a zone near the fiber matrix interface. Nickel is the most active element in enhancing recrystallization. A diffusion dependent decrease in creep strength would be expected because the fibrous substructure is destroyed by recrystallization. This has been demonstrated by Petrasek and co-workers (10-13) in creep test on tungsten/copper alloys or tungsten/superalloy composites. Grunling and Hofer (14) measured the depth of the recrystallized zone into tungsten and W-2% ThO₂ wire in Ni and NiCr matrix alloys at 1000-1200°C. The depth of recrystallization as a function of time at temperature followed a parabolic rate law (exponent of ~.5) for the W/NiCr and W-2% ThO₂/NiCr alloys. The activation energy controlling the process in W/NiCr and W-2% ThO₂/NiCr was 78 and 90 kcal respectively, which is only slightly higher than the activation energy for grain boundary diffusion in tungsten.

Jones (9) examined the interface region of cold worked doped tungsten/nickel composites with the direct imaging ion probe mass spectrometer (DIMA) and observed Ni to be concentrated on grain boundaries in the newly created recrystallized structure in tungsten, thus confirming Grunling and Hofer's observations.

From the above references, it is concluded that W recrystallization via Ni/W interdiffusion will limit the useful life of W or W-alloy fiber/Ni base alloy matrix composites. We have only two alternatives for longer time applications required for land base gas turbine blades. They are 1) alter matrix to reduce the activity of Ni (or other interdiffusing elements) or 2) apply a barrier at the fiber/matrix interface.

The first option has been explored by NASA and has resulted in the development of the high tungsten content superalloy NAS3-25 which is compatible for up to 1000 hrs. at 1093°C (2000°F). The life requirements for land based gas turbine engines is in excess of 15,000 hrs. This coupled with the matrix density increase makes this option unacceptable.

The diffusion barrier approach was selected as the most promising solution to the problem. Earlier work on TaC and Ta₂C barriers (16) showed that although the resistance to Ni enhanced recrystallization was insufficient, the degree of protection (retardation of Ni interdiffusion) was proportional to the free energy of formation of the barrier compound. With this lesson in hand, the chemical potential vs. temperature plots of a number of carbides and oxides may be examined. The most promising candidates are shown in Figures 2 and 3.

HfC would be the most stable carbide based on our previous experience with TaC and Ta₂C and on the free energy plots of Figure 2, and would be the most likely compound to withstand the environment between tungsten and the Mar-M-200 matrix at temperatures approaching 1200°C. HfC was chosen as a candidate material and TiC was chosen as a further reference for verifying the trend of increased compatibility with increased chemical potential.

Fig. 2 -- Chemical potential of carbon for selected carbides

Fig. 3 -- Standard free energy of formation of selected oxides for the reaction $2 \frac{x}{y} \text{M} + \text{O}_2 \rightleftharpoons 2 \frac{y}{x} \text{M}_x\text{O}_y$

Oxides are, in general, very stable. However, oxides are quite mobile and exhibit semiconductor properties due to defect structures at the temperature envisioned for the intended application. Further, it is difficult to maintain purity of the oxides since an inexhaustible supply of dopants of various types exist within the matrix. A related consideration in utilizing oxides as diffusion barriers is the phenomenon of oxide alloying with oxide impurities in the matrix. Consider argon atomized superalloys, for example. Oxide impurities in the form of Al_2O_3 or possibly spinels are present on powder surfaces. These oxides may alloy with the oxide barrier on tungsten wire and result in increased diffusivity of matrix constituents. Nevertheless, it was decided to include three oxides in this study based on the chemical potential vs. temperature plot of Figure 3. The candidates all having about the same free energy of formation are Al_2O_3 , Y_2O_3 and HfO_2 .

Titanium nitride, applied by CVD to 0.015 in. dia. W-1% ThO_2 wire became available at the onset of this study and was evaluated along with the other barrier candidates. Thermo-physical properties of the candidate materials and related oxides, carbides and nitrides are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1
THERMAL AND CHEMICAL STABILITY DATA

Species	Thermal Expansion Coefficient $\times 10^6/^\circ C$	Temp Range $^\circ C$		$-\Delta G$ kcal 1500
<u>Fiber</u>				
W	6.4	20	2000	--
<u>Matrix</u>				
Mar-M-200	12.1	20	204	--
	12.7	20	426	
	13.5	20	650	
	16.5	20	870	
	17.4	20	1093	
<u>Carbides</u>				
TiC	7.74	20	270	39
ZrC	6.73	20	1100	43
HfC	6.59	20	600	47
TaC	6.29	20	1100	34
Wc	3.84	20	400	8
<u>Oxides</u>				
Al_2O_3	9.0	20	982	202
Y_2O_3	8.5	20	1098	207
TiO_2	4.9	20	1093	160
ZrO_2	7.9	20	1093	197
HfO_2	5.6	20	1093	204
Cr_2O_3	6.9	20	1093	108
<u>Nitrides</u>				
TiN	8.1	20	600	47
	9.0	600	1400	
ZrN	7.0	20	600	53
	7.7	600	1400	
HfN	6.5	20	1400	56

Experimental Techniques

Trace amounts of Ni diffusing from the matrix into tungsten wire will result in recrystallization of a zone near the wire periphery at the application temperature envisioned for composites. The interface between

the wrought appearing wire core and the recrystallized periphery can be taken as the locus of the specific (but not necessarily defined) concentration of Ni required to produce recrystallization at a given temperature. Compatibility, for our purposes, is measured by the depth of the recrystallization zone below the original barrier candidate/tungsten wire interface. This depth would also include any surface recession due to growth of intermediate phases between the barrier and matrix.

The diffusion barrier candidates, with the exception of CVD coated TiN, were applied to the wire surface by rf sputtering. The sputter targets were hot-pressed oxides and carbides attached to 6 in. diameter copper adaptors by use of a conductive epoxy. Uniform thickness of deposition on wire surfaces was accomplished by rotating the wires under the rf sputtering target. A rig was designed in which the wires were located at the periphery of two wheels forming a "squirrel cage-like" configuration as shown in Figure 4. The assembly was rotated by a small motor mounted remote from the deposition area.

Fig. 4 -- Rotation jig for sputter deposition on wire surface.

Diffusion couples were made by surrounding barrier coated wires in argon atomized Mar-M-200 matrix alloy powder in a 304 SS tube. The vendor chemistry of the Mar-M-200 powder lot used in this study is given in Table 2. The tube was evacuated and sealed and hot isostatically pressed at 1120°C (2050°F) at 69 MPa (10 ksi). Heating time at pressure was two hours. The resultant compact was sectioned and placed in quartz tubes, evacuated, and sealed. The couples were thermally exposed for times to 2000 hrs. at 1066°C (1950°F), 1120°C (2050°F) and 1177°C (2150°F). The tungsten substructure was revealed by a light Murakami's etch. A 10% chromic acid-electrolytic etch was utilized to reveal the matrix substructure. Neither of these etchants affected the coatings.

Kinetics of Diffusion Barrier Decomposition

The measured depths of Ni penetration through the barrier into the tungsten wire as indicated by a peripheral recrystallized zone at the 1066°C (1950°F), 1121°C (2050°F) and 1177°C (2150°F) isotherms are given in Tables 3, 4 and 5 respectively. There is considerable scatter in the data in that smooth thickness vs. time plots are not always obtained. However, when oxides are taken as a group, the log depth vs. log time plot fall within a band with a slope of .5 as shown in Figure 5 for the 1177°C (2150°F) isotherm. The uncoated Mar-M-200/HSTW control also demonstrated parabolic growth characteristics.

Hafnium carbide was the best coating evaluated. Very little reaction was noted after 2000 hrs. at 1177°F (2150°F) as shown in Figure 5. The 16 μ m of reaction was largely due to growth of intermediate zones between the coating and tungsten wire rather than recrystallization per-se.

Microscopic Evaluation

An evaluation of the microstructure produced by long time exposure at the application temperature is necessary for the proper understanding of barrier behavior. Several techniques, including SEM, electron microprobe analysis, energy dispersive x-ray analysis, and Auger electron spectroscopy were utilized in this study.

TABLE 2
MAR-M-200 MATRIX VENDOR CHEMISTRY ANALYSIS
Powder Lot R73033

	<u>Nominal</u>	<u>Actual</u>		<u>Nominal</u>	<u>Actual</u>
Ni		59.3%	C	.15	.16
W	12.5	12.41	N ₂	--	.0027
Co	10.0	10.12	O ₂	--	.0152
Cr	9.0	9.52	S	--	.021
Al	5.0	5.16	B	.015	.013
Nb	1.0	1.03			
Ti	2.0	1.95			
Fe	--	.21			
Zr	.05	.03			
Si	--	.10			

TABLE 3
DEPTH OF RECRYSTALLIZED ZONE BELOW ORIGINAL
HSTW/BARRIER INTERFACE AFTER HEATING AT 1066°C (1950°F)

<u>Time-Hrs.</u>	<u>Barrier Candidate</u>					
	<u>HfO₂</u>	<u>Y₂O₃</u>	<u>Al₂O₃</u>	<u>TiC</u>	<u>TiN</u>	<u>HfC</u>
10	NR*	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR
30	NR	NR	NR	7 m	5 m	NR
100	NR	NR	NR	11	9	NR
312	NR	NR	NR	15	16	NR
1048	NR	NR	NR	25	27	NR

TABLE 4
DEPTH OF RECRYSTALLIZED ZONE BELOW ORIGINAL
HSTW/BARRIER INTERFACE AFTER HEATING AT 1121°C (2050°F)

<u>Time-Hrs.</u>	<u>Uncoated HSTW</u>	<u>Barrier Candidate</u>					<u>HfC</u>
		<u>HfO₂</u>	<u>Y₂O₃</u>	<u>Al₂O₃</u>	<u>TiC</u>	<u>TiN</u>	
30	18 m	NR*	5 m	105 m	15	14	NR
100	40	10 m	9	14	32	26	NR
312	63	27	11	16	60	52	NR
1048	130	--	--	--	--	--	NR

TABLE 5
DEPTH OF RECRYSTALLIZED ZONE BELOW ORIGINAL
HSTW/BARRIER INTERFACE AFTER HEATING AT 1177°C (2150°F)

<u>Time-Hrs.</u>	<u>Uncoated HSTW</u>	<u>HfO₂</u>	<u>Y₂O₃</u>	<u>Al₂O₃</u>	<u>TiC</u>	<u>TiN</u>	<u>HfC</u>
		10	--	NR*	NR	NR	16 m
30	20 m	9 m	6 m	9 m	20	16.5	NR
100	42 m	15	10	14	24	32	NR
312	76	27	32	23	50	100	10 m
1048	--	52	46	35	115	CR**	15 m
2000	--	80	75	58	190	CR**	16 m

*NR - No recrystallization noted
**CR - Completely recrystallized

As Coated

Specimens of the as-coated wire were electroplated with Ni and polished to reveal the coating structure and thickness as shown in Figures 6 and 7. The thicknesses are tabulated below:

Fig. 5 -- Kinetic data from 2150°F diffusion barrier study.

Al ₂ O ₃	3.5 μm
Y ₂ O ₃	4.5
HfO ₂	4
TiC	7
TiW	5.5
HfC	12.5

The coating morphology is largely determined by the surface roughness of the wire substrate. Sputter grown deposits tend by nature to columnar growth. A rough surface results in defects such as void entrapment and a lumpy surface as shown in Figures 6 and 7. This type of structure is not ideal for barrier applications because the long columnar grain boundaries provide easy diffusion paths. The CVD TiN coating appeared to be of more equiaxed grain structure. The cavities of Figure 7 are due to pull-out during polishing. Nevertheless, the coatings produced seemed to be of adequate integrity to proceed with compatibility experiments.

As HIP

The microstructure of most coatings begin to change immediately upon thermal exposure. New phases appear at both barrier/matrix and barrier/tungsten interfaces as shown for Y₂O₃ and HfO₂ in Figure 8 and for TiC and HfC in Figure 9. Very little change is noted in the Al₂O₃ or TiN coatings after the HIP consolidation thermal exposure. The columnar structure of the sputter deposited coatings lead to rather serious defects as seen for HfO₂ in Figure 8 and for HfC in Figure 10. Thermal expansion differences also appear to play a part in debonding and actual overlap occasionally observed and recorded in Figure 10.

Microstructure of Thermally Exposed Compatibility Specimens

A general observation from this investigation is that a barrier need not be inert to be effective. All of the barriers changed radically in their structure or composition. In some cases, this change was accompanied by Ni penetration into the tungsten wire, inevitably causing recrystallization.

Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃

The microstructure of the Y₂O₃ and Al₂O₃ coatings are similar as shown in Figures 11 and 12 for couples exposed 2000 hrs. at 1177°C (2150°F). Neither coating maintained its original structure. Oxide alloying or spinel formation with matrix impurities is evident from the SEM photomicrographs. An intermetallic phase was formed at the Y₂O₃ coating/W wire interface as shown in Figure 12. The drastic change in microstructure was accompanied by Ni enhanced recrystallization of the tungsten to a depth of 58 μm and 75 μm for the Al₂O₃ and Y₂O₃ coated specimen respectively.

HfO₂

Hafnium oxide did not fare any better as a diffusion barrier than the other oxides examined here. However, it was examined in greater detail than Y₂O₃ or Al₂O₃ barriers because of its similarity in decomposition and reaction product formation to the more successful HfC coating. The depth of tungsten recrystallization due to Ni transport through the hafnia after 2000 hrs. at 1177°C (2150°F) was an unacceptable 80 μm. The microstructure shown in Figure 13 shows the formation of distinct intermediate phases at both the matrix and tungsten interface.

Al₂O₃ thickness
-3.5 μm

Al₂O₃
2000X

Y₂O₃ thickness
4.5 μm

Y₂O₃
2000X

HfO₂ thickness
4 μm

HfO₂
2000X

Fig. 6 -- SEM photomicrographs of Al₂O₃, Y₂O₃ and HfO₂ diffusion barrier candidates after rf sputtering onto HSTW (tungsten) wire surface.

TiC thickness
7 μm

TiC
2000X

TiN thickness
5.5 μm

TiN
2000X

HfC thickness
12.5 μm

HfC
2000X

Fig. 7 -- SEM photomicrographs of TiC and HfC diffusion barrier candidates after rf sputtering onto HSTW (tungsten) wire surface. TiN was deposited on tungsten by CVD.

Al₂O₃
2000X

Y₂O₃
2000X

HfO₂
2000X

Fig. 8 -- SEM microstructure of rf sputter deposited Al₂O₃, Y₂O₃ and HfO₂ after HIP consolidating with argon atomized Mar-M-200 at 1120°C (2050°F), 69 MPa (10 ksi), 2 hrs cycle.

TiC
2000X

TiN
2000X

HfC
2000X

Fig. 9 -- SEM micrographs of TiC, TiN and HfC coated HSTW wire after HIP consolidation 2 hrs at 1120°C (1050°F) 69 MPa (10 ksi) with Mar-M-200 (argon atomized) matrix.

200X

400X

Fig. 10 -- Varieties of HIP and rf sputter deposition related coating defects for HfC coated HSTW.

1000X

Fig. 11 - SEM photomicrographs of specimen A-14 Al_2O_3 coated HSTW in Mar-M-200 after 2000 hrs at 1177°C (2150°F).

Fig. 12 -- SEM micrographs of specimen B-16 Y_2O_3 coated HSTW in Mar-M-200 after 2000 hrs at 1177°C (2150°F).

An electron microprobe analysis was conducted on this specimen and scanning x-ray micrographs are shown in Figure 14. The Hf from the original HfO_2 has remained intact. However, copious precipitation of an Al rich phase was noted at both the tungsten and matrix interfaces. The Al rich phase is most likely Al_2O_3 or a Al_2O_3 rich mixed oxide.

TiC

Titanium carbide was most decidedly unstable and unsuitable as a diffusion barrier. Extensive recrystallization occurred in the tungsten at times as short as 100 hrs. at 1177°C (2150°F). This composition appeared to be sus-

2000X

Fig. 13 -- SEM micrographs of specimen C-17 HfO_2 coated HSTW in Mar-M-200 after 2000 hrs at 1177°C (2150°F).

ceptible to mechanical damage due to thermal stresses as shown in Figure 15. The as-deposited and as HIP structure noted earlier were not as sound appearing as the HfC coating, indicating that the poor behavior may have been due to a poor application. Nevertheless, little additional effort was given to the analysis of this candidate.

1000X

Fig. 15 -- SEM photomicrographs of specimen D-15 TiC coated HSTW in Mar-M-200 after 100 hrs at 1120°C (2050°F).

TiN

TiN, in contrast to TiC, maintained its integrity through prolonged heating at 1177°C (2150°F) without changing significantly in appearance from the as HIP structure. Unfortunately, TiN, though unaffected by the matrix constituents, proved to be of little value in limiting the passage

Fig. 14 -- Scanning x-ray micrographs of specimen C-17, HfO_2 coated HSTW/Mar-M-200 diffusion couple after 2000 hrs exposure at 1177°C (2150°F).

of Ni to the HSTW wire. The promise of greater barrier effectiveness from other nitrides such as HfN lead us to evaluate this nitride in greater detail.

Figure 16 shows the microstructure of a TiN coated 0.015 in. diameter K-metal tungsten wire (K metal = W-1% ThO₂) in the Mar-M-200 matrix after 100 hrs. at 1177°C (2150°F). The coating is largely intact and unaltered. However, intermediate zones are observed at both wire and matrix interfaces. Energy dispersive x-ray analyses were performed at the spots and areas indicated in Figure 16. Counts above background for the various matrix and coating constituents are noted in the table of Figure 16. None of the matrix or wire constituents were detected in the TiN coating from area C. By contrast, the zone adjacent to the wire (spot B) showed considerable amounts of the matrix constituents Cr, Co and Ni. Likewise, the intermediate zone between the TiN coating and the matrix (spot D) showed significantly higher Al, tungsten and Ti than the matrix (area E) and a trace amount of Ni and Cr.

2000X

Area	Counts Above Background					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
Elem - radiation						
Al k α	200	--	--	1300	300	200
W m α	3800	3800		1500	900	3800
Ti k α	--	180	3900	3800	250	100
Cr k α	30	350	--	30	1150	500
Co k α	--	200	--	--	775	250
Ni k α	10	450	--	150	3800	700

Fig. 16 -- Scanning electron micrograph and energy dispersive x-ray analysis of specimen E-23, TiN coated .015 in. dia. k metal wire (W-1% ThO₂) after 100 hrs exposure at 1177°C (2150°F).

HFC

Hafnium carbide proved to be the one coating that truly retarded diffusion. Only 16 μ m of total surface recession plus recrystallized zone was measured after 2000 hrs. at 1177°C (2150°F). From the SEM photomicrograph of Figure 17, we see that 4 μ m represents surface recession due to the formation of an

intermediate zone. Scanning x-ray micrographs of Figure 17 reveal the intermediate zone between the matrix, and the wire is Cr and W rich. Aluminum appears to be concentrated in the dark appearing zone at the matrix interface.

Fig. 17 - HFC on Tungsten Wire in Mar-M200 2000 Hr/1175°C

The nature of the alteration of the original HFC coating is somewhat clarified by the energy dispersive x-ray analysis of this same specimen in Figure 18. Area A gives the usual counts above background for Mar-M-200. Tungsten-chrome carbides of the type M_6C most likely explain the high tungsten and Cr count for the precipitate of spot B. The intermediate phase band represented by spot C proved to be very rich in Al with traces of Cr, Ti and Ni present. This phase is most likely a spinel. The columnar grain boundaries provided a nucleation and growth site for two distinct phases. The phase nearest the matrix interface represented by spot D appears to be a

mixed oxide of Al, Hf, Cr and Ti. The second phase deeper into the coating represented by spot F showed only Hafnium. We would presume this phase to be HfO_2 . The main body of the coating (area E) is primarily composed of Hf but significant impurities of Cr, Ti and Ni are also present. A slight concentration of Cr, Ti and Ni was found in the interface between the original coating and the intermediate zone (spot G). Surprisingly, only Cr and tungsten are noted in the intermediate zone (spot H) between the coating and the wire. A small amount of Ni was detected near the outer surface of the tungsten wire in the ($12 \mu\text{m}$ thick) recrystallized zone (not revealed by etching in Figure 18).

F-21

67285

Peak Height - Counts Above Background

Area Analyzed	Al $k\alpha$	W $m-\alpha$	Hf $m\alpha$	Cr $k\alpha$	Ti $k\alpha$	Co $k\alpha$	Ni $k\alpha$
Area B (Matrix)	706	674	--	746	370	600	3700
Spot B	--	3700	--	453	66	185	510
Spot C	3800	--	--	50	55	--	166
Spot D	3750	--	1075	370	210	--	40
Area E	--	--	3650	34	60	--	34
Spot F	--	--	3650	--	--	--	--
Spot G	--	--	3650	100	170	--	110
Spot H	256	3800	--	465	--	--	--
Spot I	191	3700	--	106	100	--	--
Spot J	235	3700	--	--	--	--	61

Fig. 18 -- Energy dispersive x-ray analysis of areas indicated in SEM photomicrograph of F-21 - 2000 hrs at 2150°F.

The area of Figure 18, when x-ray scanned in the electron microprobe for carbon and oxygen revealed the absence of carbon. X-ray fluorescence is not a sensitive method for detecting light elements. Therefore, this specimen was evaluated by Auger electron spectroscopy. Some interesting and provocative effects were observed on the scanning Auger micrographs shown in Figures 19 and 20. Cr which was enriched in the intermediate zone (spot H of Figure 18) was not detected on the Auger spectrometer. Strong

oxygen and weak carbon indications were observed within the original coating. Aluminum appears quite strongly in the coating region when the spectrometer is set for the oxide peak shift of 1390 eV (lower half of Al scanning micrograph of Figure 20) as opposed to a general δ ' existence of Al throughout the matrix as revealed by the 1396 eV scanning micrograph of the upper half of Figure 20.

The analysis of this specimen is completed with the scanning electron micrograph of the sputter cleaned area examined by Auger spectroscopy in Figure 21. The coating gives charged contrast effects which are characteristic of non-conductors.

Fig. 19 -- Scanning Auger electron micrographs of specimen F-21 after 2000 hrs at 1177°C (2150°F).

SPECIMEN
CURRENT

Hf

F - 21

Al 1396

0

Al 1390

$E_p = 5 \text{ kV}$
 $V_{MO} = 6 \text{ kV}$
 MAG...250 X

AUGER LINES
 0...510 eV
 Hf...1617 eV
 Al...1396 eV
 ...1390 eV
 (WHILE
 SPUTTERING)

Fig. 20 -- Scanning Auger electron micrographs of specimen F-21 after 2000 hrs at 1177°C (2150°F).

1000 x

Fig. 21 -- Scanning electron micrograph of specimen F-21 (2000 hrs at 1177°C (2150°F)) showing sputtering damage during Auger microscopic analysis. Charging effects of barrier region indicates nonconducting material.

X-ray diffraction of the coating scrapped from a tungsten wire extracted from this sample revealed the presence of HfO_2 , HfSiO_4 and $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-}2\text{SiO}_2$. HfC was not detected. We must conclude from these observations that HfC has completely transformed to oxide and oxysilicates during the thermal exposure.

Discussion

Composite materials hold promise for a 200 to 300°F increase in turbine operating temperature with uncooled components. The resultant improvement in efficiency would be significant. There have been three major technical problems that cause caution in the rush to take advantage of these materials:

- . corrosion-oxidation at the increase TIT
- . thermal cycling - thermal fatigue-creep interactions
- . fiber-matrix compatibility

All other technical problems such as fabrication and lay up design are dependent upon or secondary to the three critical problems listed above. Future materials work on composite gas turbine blades should be concentrated on these problems and not be concerned with the more general fabrication and design concerns until we have sufficient data to effect meaningful designs.

We have addressed the compatibility question in this paper and we have shown that a solution to this problem exists. However, we must state that we have not developed a barrier during this work. We have sifted through a number of likely candidates and have found one -- HfC -- that provides protection for at least 2000 hrs. at 1177°C (2150°F). We have observed peculiarities in the behavior of this barrier during thermal exposure and have raised as many questions as we have answered.

Further work on barrier development should be directed toward a number of fundamental concerns. A few of the specific areas we recommend more intensive work on are as follows:

1. Effect of matrix impurities on barrier stability (C, O, N, Si, S).
2. Effect of barrier stoichiometry on stability.
3. Detailed identification of in-situ transformation products.

4. Study effect of barrier coating structure on compatibility.
5. Stability and effectiveness of barrier during thermal cycling.

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